

Diphenyl Carbazide and Diphenyl Carbazone : Part III. Spectrophotometric Titration of Diphenyl Carbazide with Chromic Acid

Nripendra Nath Ghosh and Jatindra Nath Ray

Results on spectrophotometric titration of diphenyl carbazide with a standard solution of potassium dichromate in presence of dilute sulphuric acid indicate the formation of three different coloured species by reacting Cr(VI) and diphenyl carbazide in the molar ratios 2:15, 2:3 and 8:9. The formation of diphenyl carbazone at the early stages of reaction has been confirmed by its isolation from the reaction mixture.

Diphenyl carbazide has been used as a spectrophotometric reagent for estimation of Chromium (VI). It develops an intense purple colour with chromate in presence of dilute sulphuric acid. It has been shown¹ by Job's method of continuous variation that the colour of maximum intensity develops when chromate and diphenyl carbazide are mixed together in the molar ratio 2 : 3.

In this paper, spectrophotometric titration of diphenyl carbazide (RH_4) with a standard solution of potassium dichromate at $540 \text{ m}\mu$ in presence of dilute sulphuric acid—both direct and reverse are described. In direct titrations, by plotting optical densities of mixtures versus the molar ratios of Cr (VI) and diphenyl carbazide, there are indications of the reaction taking place in the molar ratios 2 : 3. But on plotting the ratios of optical density and volume of Cr (VI) solution against molar ratios, there are three breaks in the curve indicating the formation of three different compounds reacting in the molar ratios 2:15, 2:3, and 8:9. In the reverse titrations optical density values are plotted against molar ratios and in this case also there are three breaks as in the previous case, confirming the formation of three coloured complexes reacting in the molar ratios 2 : 15, 2 : 3 and 8 : 9.

In our previous communication² the formation of diphenyl carbazone as one of the reaction products at the early stages of the reaction had been stated on the basis of polarographic studies. This has been confirmed by isolating diphenyl carbazone from the reaction mixture.

EXPERIMENTAL

All spectrophotometric readings were noted using UVISPEK Spectrophotometer. The reagents employed were either purified by recrystallisation or were of A. R. quality.

A standard solution of diphenyl carbazide was prepared by dissolving known weight of purified diphenyl carbazide in pure acetone (25ml) and then making the volume upto 100 ml with distilled water. In the direct titration the same volume of

1. M., Bose, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1954, 10, 201 ; R. T. Pflaum and L. C., Howick, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 4862.
2. N. N. Ghosh and J. N. Ray, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 38, 319.

diphenyl carbazide solution was taken in a number of 50 ml volumetric flasks and 20 ml of 0.5N H_2SO_4 and 0.25 M K_2SO_4 solution to maintain constant ionic strength, was added to each flask. Then different amounts of a standard Cr (VI) solution were added and the volumes were made up to the mark with distilled water and the solutions were allowed to stand for about 15 minutes. The optical density of each solution was then measured using light of wave length $540 m\mu$ against water as blank. Results are given in table I. On plotting optical densities against molar ratios of Cr (VI) and RH_4 , the curve (Fig. 1) indicates that the reaction takes place in the ratio 0.67. But on plotting the ratio - optical density/volume of Cr (VI) solution against molar ratios there were three breaks in the ratios 0.132, 0.67 and 0.89 (Fig. 2).

FIG 1

FIG 2

TABLE I

Composition of the solution :

20 ml of 0.5 N H_2SO_4 and 0.25 M K_2SO_4 solution
 3 ml of 6.24×10^{-4} M diphenyl carbazide solution
 X ml of 1×10^{-4} M Cr (VI) solution

The above mixture was diluted to 50 ml with distilled water.

Vol. of Cr(VI) Soln. in ml.	Optical density.	Molar ratio Cr(VI)/ RH_4	Ratio O. D./Vol. of Cr(VI).	Vol. of Cr(VI) Soln. in ml.	Optical density	Molar ratio Cr(VI)/ RH_4	Ratio O.D./Vol. Cr(VI).
0.5	0.040	0.0267	0.0800	12.5	0.607	0.6677	0.0486
1.0	0.080	0.5342	0.0800	13.5	0.603	0.7212	0.0447
1.5	0.120	0.0801	0.0800	14.5	0.590	0.7746	0.0407
2.0	0.160	0.1068	0.0800	15.5	0.566	0.8280	0.0365
2.5	0.196	0.1335	0.0784	16.0	0.547	0.8547	0.0342
3.5	0.261	0.1869	0.0763	16.5	0.535	0.8814	0.0324
5.0	0.363	0.2671	0.0726	17.0	0.517	0.9081	0.0304
7.0	0.467	0.3739	0.0667	17.5	0.482	0.9348	0.0275
9.0	0.539	0.4807	0.0599	18.0	0.444	0.9615	0.0247
11.0	0.590	0.5876	0.0536	19.0	0.383	1.0149	0.0202
11.5	0.595	0.6143	0.0517	20.0	0.231	1.0684	0.0116
12	0.602	0.6410	0.0502	21.0	0.074	1.1218	0.0035

In the reverse titration different volumes of diphenyl carbazide solution were taken in a number of 50 ml flasks and were titrated with same volume of a standard Cr (VI) solution, after adding 20 ml of 0.5 NH_4SO_4 and 0.25 MK_2SO_4 to each flask and diluting up to the mark with distilled water. After allowing to stand for about 15 minutes, optical densities were measured as usual. The results are stated in Table II. Curves (Fig. 3) were obtained by plotting optical densities versus molar ratios, and there were three breaks at the ratio 0.13, 0.67 and 0.88.

FIG. 3

TABLE II

*Composition of the solution :*20 ml of 0.5 N H_2SO_4 and 0.25 M K_2SO_4 solution5 ml of 2×10^{-4} M Cr (VI) solutionX ml of 6.126×10^{-4} M diphenyl carbazide (RH_4) solution

The above mixture was diluted to 50 ml with distilled water.

Vol. of RH_4 soln. in ml.	Optical density	Molar ratio $\text{Cr(VI)}/\text{RH}_4$	Vol. of RH_4 soln. in ml.	Optical density	Molar ratio $\text{Cr(VI)}/\text{RH}_4$
24.0	0.812	0.0680	2.4	0.492	0.6804
21.0	0.812	0.0777	2.3	0.470	0.7098
19.0	0.812	0.0859	2.2	0.449	0.7420
15.0	0.812	0.1088	2.1	0.421	0.7770
13.0	0.799	0.1256	2.0	0.400	0.8162
10.0	0.785	0.1632	1.9	0.372	0.8590
6.0	0.712	0.2720	1.8	0.334	0.9067
4.0	0.649	0.4081	1.7	0.292	0.9603
3.5	0.611	0.4663	1.6	0.244	1.021
3.0	0.577	0.5442	1.5	0.187	1.088
2.7	0.532	0.6045	1.4	0.122	1.166
2.5	0.509	0.653	1.3	0.044	1.256

The isolation of diphenyl carbazone, one of the products of the reaction mixture between diphenyl carbazide and chromic acid was made in the following way.

Diphenyl carbazide (5 g.) was dissolved in acetone (140 ml) and to this solution 2N H_2SO_4 (50 ml) was added. The resulting solution was slowly titrated under vigorous stirring with 0.37 molar Cr (VI) solution (36 ml). The time required for titration was about an hour. After addition of dichromate solution, stirring was continued for a further period of 30 minutes. The resulting mixture was poured on ice-cold water (1.5 l) saturated with sodium sulphate. Repeated extractions with ether were made till the ethereal extract was almost colourless. The combined ethereal extracts were successively washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and distilled water. A light yellow solid separated which was collected, m.p. 157° . The extract after collection of the solid was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, ether distilled off and the residue dissolved in acetone. The acetone solution was then slowly passed through a column of activated charcoal (height 21.5 cm ; cross-section 1.07 sq. cm.) soaked with acetone and thereby the dissolved products were adsorbed and then on elution with acetone at the rate of 0.85 ml per minute, the orange-coloured fraction was collected, which on evaporation left a solid residue. It was crystallised from ether, m.p. $126^\circ-7^\circ$.

The identity of the products, m.p. 157° as the double compound of diphenyl carbazide and diphenyl carbazone, and m.p. $126^\circ - 7^\circ$ as diphenyl carbazone was confirmed by analysis following the method developed by us^a.

INORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY,
CALCUTTA-9

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3. N. N. Ghosh and J. N. Ray, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 37, 650.